
Marlowe: Stanford’s GPU-based Computational Instrument

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ABSTRACT

We provide a brief overview of Marlowe, a new shared computational instrument at Stanford University that came online in the fall of 2024. Marlowe aims to provide the Stanford community substantial computational capabilities needed in modern data science, artificial intelligence research as well a wide range of scientific domains. We describe Marlowe’s architecture, operating principles, and how it fits in the broader high performance computing infrastructure at Stanford.

Keywords High-Performance Computing · HPC · Computational Science · GPU · Data Science

1 Introduction

Stanford University has historically been a leader in data-intensive and computational research. Recognizing the role that computing plays in research and education, the university has invested significant resources in high performance computing infrastructure.

Data-intensive computing and artificial intelligence research has become increasingly reliant on heavy use of GPU computing power since it takes in and processes large amounts of data. The scale of modern experiments has made computational research become very expensive, and academic researchers are held back by insufficient access to modern research computing, which now spans hardware, software, and personnel. Although cloud computing platforms like Google, AWS, and Azure, can provide GPU-cycles, economic realities of academic research have forced a number of institutions to build shared facilities for use by their communities. Marlowe is Stanford’s resource for shared large-scale GPU-computing.

2 System Architecture

2.1 Hardware Configuration

Marlowe is an NVIDIA DGX H100 Superpod, built using NVIDIA’s reference architecture, designed to deliver cutting-edge computational performance. It comprises 31 NVIDIA H100 nodes, collectively providing 248 NVIDIA H100 GPUs and 2.5PB of high-performance DDN Lustre storage.

*Marlowe is made possible with financial support from Stanford University’s Office of the President and Provost.

Each **NVIDIA DGX H100 node** includes:

- **GPU:** 8x NVIDIA H100 80GB GPUs
- **CPU:** 2x Intel Xeon Platinum 8480C CPUs (112 cores/node)
- **Memory:** 2TB of RAM
- **NVSwitch:** 4x NVLink connections, providing up to 900 GB/s GPU-to-GPU bandwidth
- **Node-local Storage:** 30TB NVMe
- **Networking:** 8x 400Gbps NDR InfiniBand connections, providing up to 3.2Tbps bandwidth

Marlowe is based on the NVIDIA's *rail-optimized* **NVIDIA reference architecture** ensuring high performance by using dedicated paths for data traffic. This design offers significant resiliency, capable of withstanding up to two leaf switch failures without compromising operational or network integrity.

DGX H100/200 System Topology

The following figure shows the DGX H100/H200 system topology.

Figure 1: NIC and GPU Affinity Diagram

Figure 1 shows the architecture diagram of the NIC and GPU affinities in a single DGX system, useful information in low-level programming for maximal performance.

2.2 Software Stack

Marlowe leverages NVIDIA's software stack and operating system. It uses Slurm for job scheduling, offers containerized tools (e.g., Apptainer) as well as the NVIDIA AI and scientific libraries. **Open OnDemand** and a variety of applications have been installed at user-request via the modules environment. The software environment will continue to expand as needed.

3 Operating Principles

Marlowe's primary use is intended to be as a "capability cluster" to support large-scale computational projects, while at the same time maintaining high resource utilization. Its homogeneous node hardware provides consistent performance

and efficiency for large-scale parallel workloads, distinguishing it from Stanford's very successful [Sherlock](#) "capacity cluster", which features heterogeneous nodes that principal investigators may invest in over time.

In addition, Marlowe's governance is tailored to support large projects ensuring its computational resources are used effectively and align with its intended purpose.

Access to Marlowe is managed through an approved PI model, requiring an application process and annual reviews to maintain access and ensure workload suitability. Large projects must undergo additional computational suitability and scientific reviews to ensure optimal use of resources.

4 Discussion

Marlowe is designed to play a key role in the ladder of computing available at Stanford and nationally, sitting somewhere above a large HPC cluster typically found at universities, but below a national computing facility. Users typically start with code that runs on their laptop, graduating to perhaps a more powerful department server, then HPC or cloud servers where parallelism may be exploited, and sometimes finally on to a leadership-class system. Ideally, jobs best suited for Marlowe have demonstrated feasibility and viability of code via the lower rungs. A team of Research Data Scientists in [Stanford Data Science](#) are available to conduct suitability reviews and also help design code and workflows for maximal system performance. The goal is to assist research groups and provide software tools so that they are easily able to follow best software engineering and open science practices with particular attention to reproducibility and portability.

5 Benchmarks

The HPL benchmark was run on Marlowe, performance across up to 30 nodes is shown in the Figure 2 below. This would have placed Marlowe in the 86th position on the [Top500 List of HPC systems, June of 2024](#), at the time of testing.

		HPL w/ 30 HGX-H100 nodes				
	No of Nodes per job	Hosts (2)	Max FLOPS (GFlop/s)	Min FLOPS (GFlop/s)	% Perf Variation (1)	Scaling Efficiency
8/9/2024	1	n[01-31]	373900.0	368600.0	1.42%	
	2	n[01-31]	774200.0	774200.0	1.55%	103.53%
	4	n[01-31]	1537000.0	1524000.0	0.85%	102.77%
	8	n[01-31]	3089000.0	3059000.0	0.97%	103.27%
	16	n[01-31]	6079000.0	6022000.0	0.94%	101.61%
	30	n[01-31]	11110000.0	11080000.0	0.27%	99.04%
<p>1. % Performance Variation is measured as $(\text{MaxPerf} - \text{MinPerf}) / \text{MaxPerf}$. Scaling Efficiency is based on maximum measured flops relative to the single node result $((N_Node_Perf / 1_Node_Perf) / \text{Num_Nodes})$</p> <p>2. HPL tests run across an even # of systems, this test was done using randomization to ensure that all hosts are included given the odd # of systems available</p>						

Figure 2: HPL Benchmarks

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